

fabryka

A web application for easily analysing & exploring the fabric of archaeological assemblages

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Abstract

This article presents fabryka 1.1, an open access R shiny web application dedicated to the fabric analysis of archaeological or geological assemblages. The fabric is a statistic made of the orientation and dip of elongated particles and archaeological objects. It provides information about the nature of the geological processes involved in the formation of the deposits and their impact on the preservation of the archaeological assemblages. This statistical analysis is not easily accessible to non-specialists and is particularly time-consuming, sometimes requiring the use of several software, some of which are chargeable. fabryka uses classical analytical procedures (Benn, rose, Schmidt and Woodcock diagrams and statistical tests on orientations) for analysing the fabrics of objects and includes a spatial method. New statistical methods and new ways of exploration are proposed in the application and in this present article.

You can use fabryka by following this link <https://marchaeologist.shinyapps.io/fabryka/> or by launching the application in Rstudio thanks to its script. The fabryka application files, made in R (Team 2025) by using the R package *shiny* (Chang et al. 2024), and this article, written in rmarkdown (Allaire et al. 2014; Xie, Allaire, and Golemund 2018; Xie, Dervieux, and Riederer 2020), are both available online in a public github repository (<https://github.com/marchaeologist/fabryka/tree/main>).

Introduction

Fabric is made of the orientation and dip of elongated objects (Bertran et al. 1997; Bertran and Lenoble 2002; Lenoble and Bertran 2004). It is a statistic (*i.e.*, it needs as much measurements as possible) that enables the identification of sedimentary processes involved in the formation of the deposits (Bertran et al. 1997; Bertran and Lenoble 2002; Lenoble and Bertran 2004) and their impact on archaeological assemblages (Isaac 1967; Schick 1986; Thomas et al. 2019). Objects abandoned by prehistoric people can be considered as sedimentary particles and are affected by natural processes (Schiffer 1983). As geological particles are often not elongated enough, analysis of the fabric of sedimentary deposits often depends mainly on archaeological material (bones and lithics). This makes it possible to identify the sedimentary processes to which they were subjected and to discuss their degree of spatial reorganization. When possible, distinguishing sedimentary particles from archaeological objects in the fabric analysis could allow to test whether these two populations were affected by different processes (*e.g.*, the fabric of an undisturbed occupation covered by deposits from a minor flood should reveal a distinct fabric from that of the alluvial pebbles on which it rests).

One of the first archaeological application probably dates to the experiments carried out by the South African G. Isaac (1967) on the shores of Lake Magadi in Kenya. G. Isaac wanted to explain the role played by hydrological processes on the bone accumulations found in the Great Rift Valley. In November 1964, he placed several concentrations of experimental material near a river branch. A few months later, heavy rains had reactivated the valley's rivers. In addition to the displacement or even loss of all or part of the material, G. Isaac revealed a reorientation that was mainly perpendicular and, to a lesser extent, parallel to the orientation of flow, with a slight upstream dip. Since G. Isaac's pioneering work, there has been an abundant literature devoted to the analysis of fabrics (Benn 1994; Lenoble and Bertran 2004; S. P. McPherron 2018) allowing this method to be increasingly performed on archaeological sites.

Numerical methods have been developed to measure the orientation and dip of objects in the field (S. J. McPherron 2005; Discamps et al. 2024) or from field archives such as plans and photos (Torre and Benito-Calvo 2013; Sánchez-Romero et al. 2016).

Two main families of statistical method are commonly used to characterize the fabric of a given assemblage (Bertran and Lenoble 2002; S. P. McPherron 2018; Torre et al. 2021).

The first methods focus on the orientation only and aim to test the null hypothesis of a random orientation of objects through several statistical tests (Krumbein 1939; Curray 1956; Rao 1967).

The second statistical method takes into account object orientation and dip. Three normalized eigenvalues (E1, E2 and E3) are calculated from the cosine formed by the axis of the artifact with the three axes of space (Watson 1966). Woodcock (1977) and Benn (1994) indices are used to describe the fabric shape. Several authors *e.g.*, (Bertran et al. 1997; Bertran and Lenoble 2002; Lenoble and Bertran 2004) built models to compare the fabric of archaeological assemblages to natural sedimentary processes and human processes (*i.e.*, fabric of knapping spots). The null hypothesis of an absence of perturbation is a fabric shape compatible with that of experimental knapping spots. These methods are described in the Mathematics section of this article.

Several software allow data processing, some of which are not freely accessible, do not allow spatial exploration of the data or do not offer interfaces to facilitate the task of non-programmer users (S. P. McPherron 2018). The following sections explain all the selected approaches and our proposals for processing the fabrics thanks to fabryka, from taking measurements in the field, through the statistical methods and graphical modes of representation used in the application (fig. 1).

Field data acquisition

During excavation, the orientation and dip of elongated remains (*i.e.* $a > 2 * b$ and with $a > 2$ cm) is measured on a representative set of artefacts or on the whole assemblage. The orientation (= bearing) of the lowest point is measured in the range $[0; 360[$ with North as the reference (*i.e.* orientation = 0°). The

Figure 1: fabryka creation scheme and organisation of the article

dip (= plunge) is measured in the range $[0; 90]$ with horizontal as a reference. The orientation $[0; 360[$ can be converted into axial data measured in the range $[0; 180[$ by subtracting 180° from the measurements in the range $[180; 360]$.

Traditionally, the azimuth of the principal axis of an object is measured using a compass considering that the point with the lowest altitude indicates the orientation of the vector. The dip is measured using an inclinometer. The aim is to measure the orientation and dip of the elongation axis of objects ignoring its shape. To do this, the measuring device must be placed parallel to the elongation axis of the object. Measuring the fabric from its imprint or visible surface is biased by its shape, making impossible to assess its true dip. Since the theodolite was introduced to excavations in the 1990s, the fabrics is sometimes measured by recording the coordinates of the ends of objects (S. J. McPherron 2005). In the latter case, the rules of trigonometry are applied to convert the pair of coordinates into orientations and dips.

Recently, speleologist have created a digital inclinometer (Leica DistoX310 modified to DistoX2; <https://paperless.bheeb.ch/>) which can be used to measure fabrics (Discamps et al. 2024). The device stores and associates data with the order of measurement. When the device is tilted downwards, the orientation of the lowest point is measured and, the recorded dip is negative. When the device is tilted upwards, the orientation of the highest point is recorded, and the dip is positive. To obtain data that is suitable for statistical analysis, in the first case the absolute value of the dip must be retained. In the second case (*i.e.* positive dip), if the measured orientation is in the interval $[0; 180]$, 180° must be added to the orientation, and if the measured orientation is in the interval $]180; 360]$, 180° must be subtracted from the orientation.

When possible, preferring the use of a digital inclinometer avoids many errors during measurement and data recording. On the other hand, for the reasons given above, the use of a theodolite to measure fabrics is not recommended as it results in inaccurate dip measurements. As well, measuring orientations and dip in sections leads to sampling biases.

A sample corresponds to all the orientation and dip measurements taken within a Lithostratigraphic Unit (LU) or a pedostratigraphic unit. These units seem to be the most coherent entity which needs to be explored because they are defined according to geological criteria, which a priori guarantee a certain coherence in terms of the formation dynamics we are seeking to approach. In fabryka, analysis are constrained within samples unless the user decides otherwise in the spatial exploration panel.

Mathematics

Classical method

Two main statistical family methods are used:

1. The first considers the orientation only. The calculation of the Vector Magnitude L (expressed as a percentage) by Curray's (1956) formula tests the hypothesis of an unimodal distribution of orientations. If the p value returned by the Rayleigh test is less than the threshold of 0.05, the null hypothesis of a random sampling from a uniform distribution is rejected. The formula for calculating the Vector Magnitude L is as follows:

Curray's formula to calculate L is:

$$L = \frac{r * 100}{n} \quad (1)$$

with:

$$r = \sqrt{\sum_{i=\alpha}^n \sin(2\alpha) + \sum_{i=\alpha}^n \cos(2\alpha)} \quad (2)$$

where n is the number of measures and α , is the axial data (0 to 180°)

The Rayleigh test is performed thanks to the formula:

$$p = e^{-(n*L^2)*10^{-4}} \quad (3)$$

The method consisting of doubling the value of the axial angles before calculating the Vector Magnitude L and the Rayleigh test, as proposed by Krumbein (1939), tests the hypothesis of a bimodal distribution with a period of 90°. The hypothesis of a 90° period bimodal distribution of a sample of orientations is retained when $p < 0.05$ (Curray 1956). The sensitivity of the Rayleigh test to the sample size n prevents samples from being compared with each other when n varies (Curray 1956; Bertran and Lenoble 2002). For example, when the Vector Magnitude L is 25%, the Rayleigh test gives p - values below a critical threshold of 0.05 for series with more than 50 measurements (fig. 2).

The Rao (1967) spacing test assesses the uniformity of circular data. It determines whether the data show significant directionality (*i.e.* the null hypothesis is a uniform distribution). It is widely used to detect multimodal directionality.

2. The second considers the orientation and dip of the objects. The normalised eigenvalues $E1$, $E2$ and $E3$ are calculated from the cosine formed by the axis of the objects with the three axes of space (Watson 1966).

The fabric shape can be described by calculating the ratios $r1 = \ln(E1/E2)$, $r2 = \ln(E2/E3)$ and $K = r1/r2$ (Woodcock 1977). When $0 < K < 1$, the fabric is planar. When $1 < K < +\infty$, the fabric is linear. The parameter $C = \ln(E1/E3)$ is a measure of the strength of the preferred orientation (Woodcock 1977). These indices can be plotted into a Woodcock diagram.

The Benn indices (Benn 1994) describe the fabric shape of a sample and can be plotted in a ternary diagram (*i.e.* Benn diagram). The elongation index EL is equal to $1 - (E2/E1)$ and the isotropy index IS is $E3/E1$. When EL is high, the axes of the objects are grouped around an orientation. When IS is high, the fabric is said to be isotropic meaning the axes of the objects are uniformly distributed in all directions. Finally,

when the value $1 - EL - IS$ is high, the fabric is said to be planar, with the axes of the objects grouped around a plane.

Figure 2: Evolution of the p-value returned by the Rayleigh test as a function of the Vector Magnitude ‘L’ and the sample size ‘n’

Spatialised method

To distinguish different statistical populations, a spatial method proposed by McPherron (2018) is used. Thanks to this method it is possible to calculate the Benn indices and the Vector Magnitude L (formula (3.) modified from McPherron (2018) R script) for each remains, and its n nearest neighbors in 3 dimensions (McPherron (2018) R script, modified, formula (4.)). The analysis of the fabric as proposed by McPherron (2018) has the advantage of spatialising the measurements. It is possible to localize the statistical signal of fabrics by varying the number of measurements sampled to calculate the Benn indices. The choice of about 40 to 60 measurements (each remain and its 40 to 60 nearest neighbors) to calculate the Benn indices allows local particularities to be observed, and above all, it allows the Rayleigh test to be carried out in its field of application (stability of the test between around 40 to 50 measurements after Bertran and Lenoble (2002)).

By avoiding the instability of the Rayleigh test, the rejection rate Tr of the null hypothesis provides a more reliable description of the distribution of orientations in a sample. In addition, it allows comparisons between samples despite varying sample size.

The rejection ratio Tr is performed thanks to the formula:

$$Tr = \frac{(n \text{ times } p.value < 0.05) * 100}{n} \quad (4)$$

Graphical representation

Several methods of representation are used. Rose diagrams summaries the orientation and dip measurements for each sample. Benn indices are projected in a Benn diagram and measures (orientation and dip) are

projected into Schmidt diagrams. These figures are available for both ‘classical’ and ‘spatialised’ methods.

As submitted by S. P. McPherron (2018), a spatial investigation of the fabric is proposed in a dedicated panel. Benn (1994) indices calculated for each spatial series of remains are projected within a Benn diagram in which each pole (isotropic, linear, and planar) is colored respectively in red, green and blue. The RGB color code is reused to materialize the fabric of the remains on spatial projections (plan and section views) of the material along the axes of the excavation grid.

Interface and user interactivity

The next sections provide a description and a tutorial of fabryka. All the figures in this section were produced using the example data set provided in the application (*i.e.* “Case 3: Angles from DistoX2 with coordinates.”)

Upload data

The simplest method to upload data in the application is to name the column names directly, as shown in the example files. Enter your data in a csv file, adding the columns ‘id’, ‘code’ and ‘sample’. If the columns don’t exist, fill them in with the same letter. By doing so, you do not need to select your variables in the main panel. The application correctly reads the data file directly.

First, upload your .csv file in the left sidebar panel (fig. 3A). Pay attention to your decimal and column delimiters (fig. 3B and C).

fabryka supports three angle measurement methods:

- angles taken with a compass and an inclinometer
- angles taken with a DistoX2
- angles taken with two shots at the total station.

Five cases (*i.e.* forms of data) are covered by the application (fig. 3D):

- check ‘Case 1: Only angles’ if you have in your data set the columns ‘id’, ‘sample’, ‘code’, ‘orientation’ and ‘dip’.
- check ‘Case 2: Only angles from DistoX2’ if you have in your data set the same columns that above but your data comes from a DistoX2 and needs to be converted.
- check ‘Case 3: Angles from DistoX2 with coordinates’ if you have in your data set the same columns that above (Case 2, data from DistoX2) with a single set of coordinates (x, y, z).
- check ‘Case 4: Angles and coordinates’ if your data has the same form that above (Case 3) but is coming from a compass and an inclinometer.
- check ‘Case 5: Two shots data without angles’ if you have the columns ‘id’, ‘sample’, ‘code’ and the angles have been measured with a total station (*i.e.* two shots data).

According to your method of angle measurement and the presence of coordinates you must select the right case. Please refer to the example files in the left side bar panel (fig. 3E). It contains a data set coming from the Lower shelter of Le Moustier (Thomas et al. 2019; Texier et al. 2020). The example files directly contain the right column names. You can use them directly in the application. Whatever the names of the columns in your file, you can select the appropriate columns in the column selector (fig. 3F). Please keep only complete lines (*i.e.* no empty modalities, so no line without a fabric measurement). When a data table with new columns appears below the column selector, you are ready to use the application.

If your data comes from a DistoX2, the columns ‘orientation’ (= ‘bearing’, *i.e.* 0 to 360°) and ‘dip’ (= ‘plunge’) are automatically corrected in the new table. Whatever the form of your data set, two new

columns 'orientation_pi' (0 to 180° angles) and 'angle_double' (see Krumbein 1939) appear. If the angles were measured using a total station (*i.e.* two shots data or 2 by 2 coordinates of plotted pieces refits), the orientation and the dip are calculated. If only one set of coordinates is provided with angles, a second set of coordinates is calculated and displayed in the new table (fig. 3G). You can download the new data by clicking the 'copy', the 'csv' or the 'pdf' buttons.

Classical method

The classical method (fig. 4) can be computed for all sources of data and absence/presence of coordinates (*i.e.* all cases described above).

Fabryka β 1.0 Presentation **Upload your data** Classical method Spatialised method Spatial exploration Markdown report Tutorial New models Bibliography

Upload your data file (.csv) ← A

Browse... Case 3_ Angles from DistoX2 with coordinates
Upload complete

Column separator ← B

Semicolon Comma Tab

Decimal separator

Comma Point ← C

What form does your dataset take? ← D

Case 1: Only angles
 Case 2: Only angles from DistoX2
 Case 3: Angles from DistoX2 with coordinates
 Case 4: Angles and coordinates
 Case 5: Two shots data without angles

Example files for each case via the links below

Case 1: Only angles
Case 2: Only angles from DistoX2
Case 3: Angles from DistoX2 with coordinates
Case 4: Angles and coordinates
Case 5: Two shots data without angles

View of the first line of your dataset

id	x	y	z	code	sample	direction	dip
7996	98.56	47.65	-1.14	FAUNE	AIII	10.26	5.00

Depending on the source and form of your data, select the appropriate columns. ← F

In any case, whatever the form of your dataset you can select your corresponding context columns.

unique 'ID' Code (e.g. silex, fauna) Sample (e.g. US, UL)

NULL NULL NULL

In cases 1, 2, 3 and 4, you must select your 'direction' and 'plunge' columns. If your direction and plunge come from a DistoX2, they will be converted to classical angles (by checking cases 2 or 3).

Direction (i.e. 0° to 360° angles) Plunge (i.e. 0° to 90° angles)

NULL NULL

In cases 3, 4 and 5, you must select your x, y and z coordinates columns.

X Y Z

NULL NULL NULL

In case 5, you must select your X2, Y2 and Z2 coordinates columns.

X2 Y2 Z2

NULL NULL NULL

View of the data that will be used in the application ← G

CSV PDF Copy Search:

id	code	sample	bearing	plunge	orientation_pi	angle_double	X1	Y1	Z1	X2	Y2
7996	FAUNE	AIII	190	5	10	20	98.562	47.65	-1.143	98.513	4
7987	FAUNE	AIII	216	1	36	72	98.725	47.767	-1.16	98.685	4
8056	SILEX	AIII	238	6	58	116	98.63	47.273	-1.137	98.604	4
8052	SILEX	AIII	281	4	101	22	98.496	47.876	-1.126	98.506	4
8010	FAUNE	AIII	313	4	133	86	98.479	47.457	-1.13	98.513	4
7674	SILEX	AIII	321	10	141	102	98.861	47.709	-1.17	98.899	4
7672	FAUNE	AIII	27	4	27	54	98.806	47.317	-1.145	98.85	4

Showing 1 to 159 of 159 entries Previous 1 Next

Figure 3: A. Browse your .csv file, B. choose your column separator, C. choose your decimal separator, D. check the right form of your dataset, E. to do so, have a look of example files, F. select the column needed in the application, G. a new dataset with new columns appears, your are ready to explore your data.

This panel includes:

- Benn diagrams with possible integration of Bertran and Lenoble (2002) model (fig. 4D)
- Rose diagrams for axial data and dip (fig. 4G)
- Schmidt diagrams (fig. 4H)
- Woodcock diagrams
- Summary data table with Benn indices, additional statistics, and orientation statistical tests.

In this last table (fig. 4I):

- N stands for number of measures in the samples
- $E1$, $E2$ and $E3$ are the eigenvalues (Watson 1966). They correspond to the sum of the cosines formed by the axis of the objects and the three axis of the space. They are used to compute the Benn indices
- IS and EL are the Benn indices ratios standing respectively for, ‘isotropy’ with $IS = E3/E1$ and ‘elongation’ with $EL = 1 - (E2/E1)$ (Benn 1994).
- K and C are the Woodcock (1977) indices.
- L is the Vector Magnitude (strength of the preferred orientation) and $R.p$ is the p-value result of the Rayleigh test.
- $L.double$ and $R.p.double$ are the same statistics that above for double angles (Krumbein 1939).
- Rao_p is the p_value of the Rao (1967) test.

You can control the data you plot and the data appearing in the figures and the summary data table by changing the checkboxes filters (‘filter by sample’ and ‘filter by code’) and the slider (*i.e.* minimum number of measures) in the left sidebar panel (fig. 4A, B and C).

The screenshot shows the Fabryka web application interface. At the top, there is a navigation bar with the following items: Fabryka β 1.0, Presentation, Upload your data, Classical method (highlighted with a red circle), Spatialised method, Spatial exploration, Markdown report, Tutorial, New models, and Bibliography. Below the navigation bar, there are four tabs: Benn diagram, Rose diagrams, Schmidt diagram, and Summary table. The main content area is divided into several sections:

- About your data:** Contains checkboxes for 'Plot all samples' and 'No code distinction'. It also has 'Filter by sample' (All, FAUNE, SILEX) and 'Filter by code' (FAUNE, SILEX) options. A slider for 'Minimum number of measures in samples to compute Benn diagram and summary table statistics' is set to 40.
- Benn diagram:** A ternary plot with vertices labeled IS, PL, and EL. It shows a blue polygon representing the data. Above the plot are three red arrows labeled G, H, and I, pointing to the Rose diagrams, Schmidt diagram, and Summary table subpanels respectively.
- Build your model:** Contains checkboxes for 'none', 'Snow Avalanche', 'Debris Flow', 'Runoff Shallow', 'Runoff Steep', 'Soilfluction', and 'Rockfall'. A red arrow labeled D points to the 'Rockfall' checkbox.
- Download your plot by choosing a file format and pressing the Download button:** Contains a 'Select a file format' section with radio buttons for 'pdf', 'png', and 'jpeg'. A red arrow labeled E points to the 'pdf' radio button. A 'Download' button is labeled with a red arrow F.

Figure 4: A. filter by sample, B. if you want to filter by codes, uncheck ‘no code distinction’, C. manage the minimum sample size to perform analysis, D. build your model thanks to Bertran and Lenoble (2002) data, E. and F. download figures by selecting a file format and pressing the ‘download’ button, G. Rose diagrams subpanel, H. Schmidt diagram subpanel, I. Summary table with additional statistics

Certain geological processes can have a different impact on objects depending on their physical properties (*e.g.* silex versus bones in a water flow as in the example files provided where bones have a strong preferential orientation and are much more ‘linear’ in the Benn diagram (Thomas et al. 2019; Texier et al. 2020)). The natural processes models that you can add to the Benn diagram are calculated using data mainly from (Bertran et al. 1997, 2006; Bertran and Lenoble 2002; Lenoble and Bertran 2004). You will find the reference model data (with corresponding literature references) which is used in the application in the ‘Model reference data’ subpanel. In the rose diagram, axial data is considered (and not orientations) as the Rayleigh test is performed on axial data (Curry 1956) in the summary table. You can download all the figures by selecting a file format (.pdf, .jpeg and .png) and pressing the ‘download’ button (fig. 4E and F).

Spatialised method

This panel includes (fig. 5):

- Benn diagrams with Benn indices computed with nearest neighbors points (S. P. McPherron 2018)
- Spatial projections of the points according to their fabric shape
- Summary data tables with orientation statistical tests, one at the scale of each spatial series (each object and its n nearest neighbors fabric = one row) and one at the scale of the sample (fig. 5F and G).

A table similar to the one done in the Classical method is proposed and contains the same statistics .

At the spatial series scale (*i.e.* each points and n neighbors), statistics are provided in a table (Spatial series data table subpanel) with the Benn indices, the orientation rates L , $L.double$ and $p - values$ returned by the Rayleigh tests. At the sample scale, mean and standard deviations values of Benn indices, mean L and its corresponding Rayleigh tests means (mean values of all spatial series in the sample) and rejections ratios Tr (formula 4.) are given in the subpanel ‘Summary table of samples’.

In the projections, the orientation of the objects can be materialized by sticks (by unchecking the corresponding box in the left sidebar panel, fig. 5D) which color is representative of the fabric of the series formed by the object and its n nearest neighbors. You can also add orthophoto in the background of projections (fig. 5E). In the left sidebar panel, you can control the samples considered in the analysis by selecting the sample explored or by distinguishing the code used (*e.g.* flint versus bone, fig. 5A and B). You can also use the slider to change the number of neighbors searched for around each point (fig. 5C). Be careful, this will alter the results obtained in the Benn diagram and Rayleigh tests.

Spatial exploration

This panel includes (fig. 6):

- A spatial exploration of your data starting from a Benn diagram
- A spatial exploration of your data starting from the spatial projections (fig. 6J)
- Summary data tables with orientation statistical tests (fig. 6I and K).

In this panel, you can perform a spatial analysis of your data starting from a Benn diagram or from projections. In both cases, you need to select the data you want to explore more locally in a new analysis. From the projections, you can select the points you want to explore directly. In the Benn diagram, you need to select the lasso selector (fig. 6D). Pay attention to the number of points selected and check that the new sample contains enough points to carry out the new analysis. If this is not the case, you can lower the slider in the left sidebar panel to perform the analysis with fewer neighbors (fig. 6E). You can download the new samples you have selected with spatial statistics from the corresponding subpanels (fig. 6I and K).

Figure 5: A. filter by sample, B. if you want to filter by code, uncheck 'no code distinction', C. choose the n nearest neighbors to perform the statistics, D. make sticks in spatial projections, E. upload a georeferenced orthophoto and check 'include' orthophoto to display it, F. new dataset at the spatial series scale, G. summary table at the sample scale.

Tutorial

The 'Tutorial' panel contains a summary of the mathematics, statistics and methods used in fabryka and a short tutorial directly accessible from the application.

New reference models

The 'spatialised' method generates often more linear fabrics in comparison with the 'classical' method. This can be explained by the fact that objects that are close in space are more likely to resemble each other than objects that are further in space. A difference between global fabric ("classical method", *i.e.*, one point per sample) and spatialised fabric (series of n neighbors) in Benn diagrams marks a spatial heterogeneity that needs to be explored.

Also, the structure of the point pattern is evocative of its fabric. Thus, the dispersion of the points depends on the shape of the fabric. Two extremes appear: the most isotropic samples are those with the most dispersed point patterns (*i.e.* the standard deviations are high) while the most linear samples are those with the least dispersed point patterns. Planar samples highlight point patterns with intermediate dispersion. The explanation of this phenomenon is intuitive: the more similar the fabrics of objects are, the closer they are in the Benn diagram and the more linear they are. To reflect this phenomenon, the standard deviations of the Benn indices are calculated and aim to describe the dispersion point patterns in the Benn diagrams.

Global planar or isotropic fabrics can sometimes mask local anisotropy. Within certain samples, groups of objects form a dense cluster in the point pattern. This is expressed either by a locally more linear fabric, or by a planar fabric with a strong bimodal orientation.

Figure 6: A. if you want to filter by sample, uncheck 'No sample distinction' B. if you want to filter by code, uncheck 'no code distinction', C. choose the n nearest neighbors to perform the statistics (first Benn diagram), E. choose the n nearest neighbors to perform the statistics on the sampled data (second Benn diagram), F. make sticks in spatial projections, G. you can upload a georeferenced orthophoto and check 'include' orthophoto to display it, H. a new spatial exploration of the fabric is performed, I. new dataset at the selected spatial series scale, I. a similar spatial exploration is possible from the projections, K. new dataset at the selected spatial series scale.

For the reasons given above, we wish to create new models that considered the particularities of the spatial method. A panel was therefore set up to collect new data describing the fabric of sedimentary processes in order to build a new "spatialised" reference model (*cf.* the "classical" model proposed by Bertran and Lenoble (2002)). This work is in progress. This panel will be updated in the next version of the application.

Contributors

The contributors panel aims at citing all contributors of this project.

Data, scripts, code, and supplementary information availability

- use fabryka online: <https://marchaeologist.shinyapps.io/fabryka/>
- source code: <https://github.com/marchaeologist/fabryka/tree/main>
- Report bugs or any request: <https://github.com/marchaeologist/fabryka/issues>
- github repository doi of fabryka: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15909666>
- Zenodo repository of this article: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16758152>

If you are preparing a mission in a field without Internet access:

1. Install R and Rstudio Desktop.
2. Clone the fabryka repository from GitHub: <https://github.com/marchaeologist/fabryka> or download the code in “Code” and “Download ZIP” at the same address. Unzip the folder. This will give you the latest version of the source code.
3. Open fabryka.Rproj
4. If you are using the application for the first time, you have to install several packages used in the application. Lists of all these packages and dependencies are available in a DESCRIPTION file and a DEPENDENCIES file in the github repository. To install fabryka packages and dependencies, copy and paste the following code lines into the R console:

```
fabryka_packages = c("shiny", "dplyr", "ggplot2", "plotly", "ggsci", "ggtern", "circular",  
                    "CircStats", "Ternary", "RStoolbox", "shinyjs", "rmarkdown",  
                    "shinythemes", "ggalt", "DT", "raster")  
  
is_installed = sapply(fabryka_packages, require, character.only=T)  
  
sapply(fabryka_packages[!is_installed], install.packages)
```

5. The application can be launched by opening the app.R file in the main folder and pressing “Run App” or by running the following commands:

```
pkgload::load_all(".")  
  
fabryka()
```

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Conflict of interest disclosure

The authors declare that they comply with the PCI rule of having no financial conflicts of interest in relation to the content of the article.

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The ‘Bibliography’ panel in the application contains the references cited in the application. This article contains the same bibliography with some additional references.

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